

Automated Knowledge Extraction and Organization of Pharmaceutical Standard Operating Procedures: A Six-Stage Pipeline Approach

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Abstract

Introduction: Standard operating procedures (SOPs) are foundational to pharmaceutical data management, yet their volume and complexity create barriers to knowledge retrieval and new-hire onboarding.

Objectives: To develop and validate an automated pipeline that transforms a pharmaceutical SOP library into a structured, navigable knowledge system with multiple output formats.

Methods: We built a six-stage pipeline: content extraction into a Unified Document Model (UDM), lifecycle-based workflow classification across 10 categories, multi-format knowledge graph generation, workflow-organized PDF eBook compilation, AI agent skill packaging, and interactive HTML exploration. Classification uses keyword matching augmented by domain expert overrides, prioritizing transparency and auditability.

Results: Applied to 253 SOPs from the biostatistics division of a large pharmaceutical company, the system achieved 100% extraction success (0 errors), produced 470 workflow assignments spanning 10 lifecycle categories, and generated a 6,620-page eBook (51.8 MB) alongside a self-contained 559 KB interactive explorer. Four knowledge graph formats (JSON-LD, hierarchical JSON, JSONL, progressive index) enable integration with graph databases, AI agents, and web applications.

Conclusions: Practical SOP knowledge automation is achievable using established document processing libraries without large language models or semantic embeddings. The architecture is replicable for pharmaceutical organizations seeking to improve SOP accessibility and lifecycle-based knowledge discovery.

Keywords: standard operating procedures, knowledge management, knowledge graph, pharmaceutical data management, clinical data lifecycle, workflow taxonomy

1 Introduction

Standard operating procedures (SOPs) are the primary regulatory instruments for pharmaceutical data management. They codify the processes that ensure data integrity, patient safety, and regulatory compliance across the clinical trial lifecycle—from study setup through regulatory submission^{1,2}. In large pharmaceutical organizations, these document libraries can grow to hundreds of SOPs, work instructions, job aids, templates, and guidance documents, each potentially referencing dozens of others through cross-citations and procedural dependencies.

Despite their importance, SOP libraries create practical problems for practitioners³. New analysts joining a biostatistics team must navigate interconnected documents to find which procedures apply to

their role and study phase. Experienced staff spend time locating correct SOP versions, tracing cross-references, and determining which documents belong to a particular workflow. Enterprise document management systems, while effective for version control and audit trails, typically offer flat search interfaces that do not capture relational structure among documents⁴.

These problems motivate automated approaches to SOP knowledge organization. Prior work in pharmaceutical document management has focused on individual aspects: document parsing, taxonomy development, or knowledge graph construction. No published system addresses the full pipeline from raw SOP documents to interactive, multi-format knowledge outputs designed for pharmaceutical data management practitioners.

This paper presents an automated six-stage pipeline that transforms a complete SOP library into a structured knowledge system. The contributions of this work are:

1. **Automated extraction pipeline:** A parser factory supporting multiple document formats (.docx, .pdf, legacy .doc) that produces a Unified Document Model capturing metadata, section hierarchy, procedure steps, tables, templates, and cross-references.
2. **Lifecycle-based workflow taxonomy:** A 10-category classification scheme aligned to the clinical trial data lifecycle, with keyword-based automated mapping augmented by domain expert overrides.
3. **Multi-format knowledge graph:** Four complementary output formats (JSONL, hierarchical JSON, JSON-LD, progressive loading index) enabling integration with diverse downstream systems including graph databases, AI agents, and web applications.
4. **Interactive knowledge explorer:** A self-contained HTML application with graph visualization, live search, and document browsing capabilities that requires no server infrastructure.

We developed and validated the system against a production library of 253 SOPs from the biostatistics division of a large pharmaceutical company. All metrics reported here reflect production results.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 SOP Management in Pharmaceutical Organizations

Standard operating procedures are required by regulatory frameworks including ICH E6(R2) Good Clinical Practice guidelines¹ and FDA 21 CFR Part 11². Pharmaceutical organizations maintain SOP libraries that span the full clinical trial lifecycle: study initiation, data collection, data transformation (including CDISC standards such as SDTM and ADaM), statistical analysis and reporting, regulatory submissions, safety monitoring, and quality assurance. The management of these document libraries is recognized as a significant operational challenge, particularly in large organizations where SOP counts may reach into the hundreds or thousands^{3;5}.

Enterprise document management systems such as those used in regulated pharmaceutical environments provide version control, access management, and audit trail capabilities. However, these systems typically present documents as flat collections searchable by metadata fields (title, document ID, effective date) without capturing the procedural and referential relationships among documents⁴.

2.2 Document Knowledge Extraction

Extracting structured knowledge from semi-structured documents is an active area in information retrieval and natural language processing. For Microsoft Word documents, the python-docx library enables programmatic access to paragraph styles, heading hierarchies, tables, and document properties⁶. PDF content extraction presents additional challenges due to the format's page-oriented structure; tools

such as PyMuPDF and pdfplumber provide complementary capabilities for text extraction and table recognition^{7:8}.

In the pharmaceutical domain, document extraction and structured authoring have been applied to clinical study reports⁹, electronic common technical document (eCTD) submissions¹⁰, and pharmacovigilance case processing¹¹. These efforts typically focus on a single document type rather than addressing the full SOP library.

2.3 Knowledge Graphs in Pharmaceutical Applications

Knowledge graphs have been applied in pharmaceutical research and operations, including drug discovery¹², adverse event signal detection¹³, and clinical trial design¹⁴. Hogan et al. survey knowledge graph techniques and applications¹⁵. However, applying knowledge graph technology to internal operational documents such as SOPs remains less explored.

JSON-LD, a W3C-recommended format for linked data, provides a pathway from document-level knowledge extraction to graph database import¹⁶. Progressive loading architectures, where a lightweight index enables on-demand retrieval of detailed subgraphs, address the scalability challenges of deploying knowledge graphs in resource-constrained environments such as browser-based applications.

2.4 CDISC Standards and Data Lifecycle Context

The Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) defines the data standards that underpin pharmaceutical data transformation workflows, including SDTM (Study Data Tabulation Model) for raw data tabulation and ADaM (Analysis Data Model) for analysis-ready datasets^{17:18}. SOPs governing these transformations form the largest category in typical biostatistics SOP libraries, reflecting the central role of data standards in regulatory submissions.

The lifecycle-based taxonomy used in this work aligns with the operational phases recognized in CDISC-compliant data management: study setup, data collection, data transformation, analysis and reporting, regulatory submission, and supporting functions (safety monitoring, quality assurance, specialized studies, external data, medical writing).

3 System Architecture

The SOP Knowledge System implements a six-stage pipeline that progressively transforms raw documents into structured, navigable knowledge outputs. Figure 1 illustrates the overall architecture.

3.1 Pipeline Overview

3.2 Design Decisions

The architecture reflects four design principles:

Format-agnostic input. The SOP library contained documents in three formats: .docx (majority), .pdf (4 native PDFs), and .doc (16 legacy files). A parser factory pattern dispatches each document to the appropriate extraction engine, producing a uniform Unified Document Model regardless of source format.

Multi-format output. Downstream consumers of SOP knowledge range from graph databases to AI agents to human readers. The pipeline generates four complementary knowledge graph formats alongside a PDF eBook and an interactive HTML explorer rather than optimizing for a single format.

Keyword-based classification with manual overrides. The workflow mapping stage uses keyword matching rather than semantic embeddings or large language models. This choice prioritizes transparency, reproducibility, and auditability—all essential properties for regulated pharmaceutical envi-

Figure 1: Six-stage pipeline architecture. Each stage consumes the output of the previous stage and produces structured artifacts that serve as inputs to subsequent stages and as standalone deliverables.

ronments. Domain experts provide manual overrides for documents that resist keyword classification, combining automation with expert judgment.

Self-contained outputs. The HTML knowledge explorer embeds all data as inline JSON within a single HTML file, requiring no server infrastructure, database connections, or build steps to deploy. This design enables distribution via email, shared drives, or intranet portals commonly used in pharmaceutical organizations.

3.3 Technology Stack

Table 1 summarizes the core technologies used across pipeline stages.

Table 1: Technology stack by pipeline stage.

Stage	Component	Technology	Purpose
1	Document scanning	Python pathlib	Recursive file discovery
1	Format conversion	pywin32 (Word COM)	.doc to .docx/.pdf conversion
2	DOCX parsing	python-docx	Paragraph styles, tables, properties
2	PDF parsing	PyMuPDF, pdfplumber	Text extraction, table recognition
3	Taxonomy definition	YAML (PyYAML)	Workflow configuration
4	Knowledge graph	Python json module	JSONL, JSON-LD, hierarchical JSON
5	PDF generation	PyMuPDF	Cover pages, TOC, PDF merging
6	Graph visualization	Cytoscape.js	Force-directed graph layout
6	Reactive UI	Alpine.js	Client-side search and filtering
6	Templating	Jinja2	HTML generation

4 Implementation

4.1 Content Extraction and Unified Document Model

The first substantive pipeline stage parses each SOP document into a Unified Document Model (UDM)—a JSON structure that captures six content categories:

- **Metadata:** document ID, title, document type (SOP, Work Instruction, Job Aid, Template, Guidance), version, effective date, owner, and source format.
- **Sections:** hierarchical section structure with nesting levels, titles, and body content.

- **Procedures:** numbered procedural steps with optional role assignments (e.g., “Statistical Programmer: Execute validation scripts”).
- **Tables:** structured table data with column headers and typed rows (checklist, role assignment, reference table, data table).
- **Templates:** identified template sections with extractable placeholder fields.
- **Cross-references:** mentions of other document IDs detected via regex pattern matching across paragraph text and hyperlinks.

A document ID regex pattern handles the diverse naming conventions found in pharmaceutical SOP libraries. The pattern captures hierarchical identifiers where the base SOP number is extended with execution resource (ER) suffixes (e.g., SOP-001, SOP-001.ER54).

A parser factory dispatches documents to format-specific parsers:

DocxParser

Uses python-docx⁶ to access paragraph styles (Heading 1–6), numbered lists, tables, core properties, and hyperlink relationships. Section hierarchy is maintained using a stack-based approach that tracks nesting levels.

PdfParser

Uses PyMuPDF⁷ for text extraction and pdfplumber⁸ for table recognition. Section detection relies on heuristic pattern matching (numbered headings, uppercase text) since PDFs lack semantic style information.

Doc conversion

Legacy .doc files are first converted to .docx via Microsoft Word COM automation (pywin32), then processed by DocxParser. A batch conversion function opens Word once and processes all files sequentially for efficiency.

The extraction stage processed 253 supported documents plus 16 converted .doc files, producing 269 UDM JSON files (185 unique documents plus 84 subdirectory duplicates) with zero extraction errors.

Figure 2 illustrates the UDM schema with an anonymized example.

4.2 Workflow Taxonomy and Mapping

The workflow taxonomy defines 10 lifecycle-based categories organized into three groups. **Study lifecycle phases:** (1) Study Setup & Planning, (2) Data Collection & Management, (3) Data Transformation (SDTM/ADaM), (4) Statistical Analysis & Reporting, (5) Regulatory Submissions, (6) Safety Monitoring & Pharmacovigilance, (7) Quality Assurance & Compliance. **Special study types:** (8) External Data & Real-World Evidence, (9) Medical Writing & Publications, (10) Special Study Types & Analyses.

Each workflow is defined in a YAML configuration file with an identifier, human-readable title, description, and a list of classification keywords. For example, the Data Transformation workflow includes keywords such as “SDTM,” “ADaM,” “dataset,” “transformation,” “CDISC,” “define.xml,” and “annotated CRF.”

Classification algorithm. For each document, the mapper extracts all searchable text from the UDM (metadata, section titles, section content, procedure actions, and sampled table content) and counts keyword matches against each workflow’s keyword list. The classification score is computed as:

$$\text{score}(d, w) = \frac{|\text{matched_keywords}(d, w)|}{|\text{keywords}(w)|} \quad (1)$$

```

{
  "metadata": {
    "doc_id": "SOP-001.ER54",
    "title": "Data Transformation Process",
    "type": "Work Instruction",
    "version": "3",
    "effective_date": "2025-11-15",
    "owner": "Data Standards Team",
    "source_format": "docx"
  },
  "sections": [ { "id": "1", "level": 1,
    "title": "Purpose", "content": "..." } ],
  "procedures": [ { "step_id": "1",
    "role": "Programmer",
    "action": "Execute transformation scripts" } ],
  "tables": [ { "id": "table_1", "type": "checklist",
    "columns": ["Step", "Complete", "Date"] } ],
  "templates": [ { "id": "template_1", "type": "email",
    "title": "Notification Template" } ],
  "cross_references": [ { "target_doc": "SOP-001.ER58",
    "reference_type": "mention" } ]
}

```

Figure 2: Unified Document Model (UDM) schema. Each extracted document produces a JSON file containing six content categories. Document IDs shown are anonymized.

where d is a document and w is a workflow. Documents scoring above a configurable threshold (default: 0.3) are assigned to that workflow. Documents may be assigned to multiple workflows, with the highest-scoring workflow designated as the primary assignment.

Manual overrides. A separate YAML configuration file allows domain experts to explicitly assign documents to workflows, overriding keyword-based classification. The production system uses 83 manual overrides, including assignments for 19 previously unmatched documents whose content did not contain sufficient keywords for automated classification and 16 converted legacy .doc files.

The mapping stage produced 470 workflow assignments across 10 workflows. Table 2 shows the distribution.

Table 2: Workflow distribution of 253 SOP documents. Documents may appear in multiple workflows; the total (470) exceeds the document count due to multi-workflow assignments.

Workflow	Documents	Share (%)
Data Transformation (SDTM/ADaM)	107	22.8
Statistical Analysis & Reporting	74	15.7
Regulatory Submissions	45	9.6
Quality Assurance & Compliance	44	9.4
Safety Monitoring & Pharmacovigilance	40	8.5
Data Collection & Management	39	8.3
Special Study Types & Analyses	38	8.1
External Data & Real-World Evidence	28	6.0
Study Setup & Planning	28	6.0
Medical Writing & Publications	27	5.7
Total	470	100.0

4.3 Knowledge Graph Generation

The knowledge graph builder consumes UDM files and workflow mappings to produce four complementary output formats:

Format 1: JSONL (Streaming). Three JSONL files contain one JSON object per line: `documents.jsonl` (document nodes with metadata and content counts), `workflows.jsonl` (workflow nodes with document lists), and `sections.jsonl` (flattened section nodes linked to parent documents). This format supports streaming ingestion by data processing pipelines.

Format 2: Hierarchical JSON (By Workflow). Ten JSON files (one per workflow) contain the complete nested structure of each workflow’s documents, including full section content, procedures, tables, templates, and cross-references. This format supports selective loading: an application can load only the workflows relevant to the current user’s role.

Format 3: JSON-LD (Graph Database Ready). A single `graph.jsonld` file encodes the complete knowledge graph using W3C JSON-LD conventions¹⁶ with a custom vocabulary namespace. Node types include Workflow, Document, and Section, with relationships including `hasPart` (workflow contains documents), `isPartOf` (section belongs to document), and `references` (cross-document citations). This format enables direct import into graph databases such as Neo4j.

Format 4: Progressive Loading Index. An `index.json` file provides lightweight metadata for all documents and workflows, including document counts, file sizes, and top-scoring documents per workflow. This index supports progressive loading patterns where a client application loads the index first, then fetches detailed workflow data on demand.

Table 3 summarizes the four output formats.

Table 3: Knowledge graph output formats and their use cases.

Format	File(s)	Size	Use Case
JSONL	<code>documents/workflows/sections.jsonl</code>	Variable	Streaming ingestion, ETL pipelines
Hierarchical JSON	<code>by_workflow/{id}.json</code> (10 files)	Variable	Selective loading by workflow
JSON-LD	<code>graph.jsonld</code>	Variable	Graph database import (Neo4j, RDF)
Progressive Index	<code>index.json</code>	Small	Fast lookup, on-demand loading

4.4 Workflow-Based eBook

The eBook builder compiles all SOP documents into a single PDF organized by workflow chapter. The generation process: (1) creates a cover page with title, subtitle, author, and date; (2) inserts a table of contents page with two-level entries (workflow chapters and individual documents); (3) for each workflow, inserts a chapter introduction page displaying the workflow title, description, and document count; (4) merges the PDF rendition of each document within the workflow chapter, preserving original formatting; (5) adds a template appendix collecting all identified templates from UDM files; (6) builds a PDF outline (bookmark tree) enabling reader navigation; and (7) adds cross-reference annotations linking related documents.

The production eBook contains 6,620 pages across 10 workflow chapters and a template appendix. To achieve full content fidelity, all 165 .docx source files were batch-converted to PDF renditions using Word COM automation prior to eBook assembly.

4.5 Agent Skill Package

The pipeline generates an AI agent skill package containing five query tools: `query_workflow` (retrieve documents by workflow), `get_document` (fetch full UDM for a specific document), `search_procedures`

(keyword search across procedures), `fill_template` (populate extracted templates with user-provided values), and `find_related` (traverse cross-reference graph from a given document). The knowledge files consist of the progressive loading index plus 10 workflow-specific JSON files, enabling the agent to answer questions about SOP content, locate relevant procedures, and navigate cross-references.

4.6 Interactive Knowledge Explorer

The final pipeline stage generates a self-contained HTML application for interactive SOP browsing. The explorer implements a three-panel layout (Figure 3):

- **Left panel:** Search input with live filtering across document titles, section headings, and workflow keywords. Workflow filter buttons with color coding. Document list with type indicators.
- **Center panel:** Force-directed graph visualization powered by Cytoscape.js¹⁹ with a cose (Compound Spring Embedder) layout. Nodes represent documents, colored by workflow assignment and sized by cross-reference count. Edges represent cross-document citations.
- **Right panel:** Document detail view showing metadata, workflow assignments, section outline, related documents, and an embedded PDF viewer.

The explorer is generated by a Jinja2 template that receives pre-computed data structures (Cytoscape elements, search index, document details, workflow metadata, PDF path mappings) as inline JSON. The resulting `index.html` file is entirely self-contained at 559 KB, requiring no external dependencies, server infrastructure, or build steps.

Visual features include dark/light mode toggle, 10 distinct workflow colors, document type shapes (ellipse for SOPs, rectangle for Work Instructions, diamond for Templates, rounded rectangle for Guidance), and node sizing proportional to cross-reference density.

Figure 3: Interactive Knowledge Explorer interface. Left panel: workflow filter buttons (color-coded) and document type checkboxes with live search. Center panel: force-directed graph visualization (Cytoscape.js) where nodes represent documents colored by primary workflow assignment; node shape indicates document type (circle for SOPs, square for Work Instructions, diamond for Templates). Right panel: document detail view showing metadata, workflow tags, and embedded PDF preview (activated on node click). Status bar shows 169 nodes, 124 edges, 10 workflows.

5 Results

5.1 Pipeline Performance

Table 4 summarizes the key metrics from the production pipeline run across the full 253-document SOP library.

Table 4: Production pipeline metrics summary.

Metric	Value
Documents scanned	253 supported + 16 .doc converted
Documents extracted (UDM)	269 total (185 unique + 84 duplicates)
Extraction errors	0
Workflow assignments	470 across 10 workflows
Manual overrides	83
Relationship edges	439
Relationship nodes	253
.doc conversions	16/16 (0 errors)
.docx-to-PDF renditions	165/165 (0 errors)

The extraction stage achieved a 100% success rate across all 253 documents with zero errors, meeting the >95% success criterion defined at project initiation. The workflow mapping stage produced 470 assignments with no unmatched documents after manual override integration, exceeding the >80% coverage target.

5.2 Workflow Distribution Analysis

The workflow distribution (Table 2) reveals that Data Transformation documents constitute the largest single category (107 assignments, 22.8%), followed by Statistical Analysis & Reporting (74, 15.7%). This distribution aligns with expectations for a biostatistics division where CDISC-compliant data processing and statistical programming are core activities.

The three smallest workflows—External Data & Real-World Evidence (28), Study Setup & Planning (28), and Medical Writing & Publications (27)—reflect specialized functions that are partially supported by other organizational units.

Multi-workflow assignments (documents appearing in more than one workflow) account for the difference between 470 total assignments and 185 unique documents. This multiplicity reflects the cross-cutting nature of many SOPs; for example, a data quality checklist may be relevant to both Data Collection and Quality Assurance workflows.

5.3 Knowledge Graph Statistics

The relationship graph contains 253 nodes and 439 edges, indicating an average of approximately 1.7 cross-references per document. The cross-reference density varies substantially across workflows, with Data Transformation and Regulatory Submission documents exhibiting the highest reference counts—consistent with the procedural dependencies inherent in these lifecycle phases.

5.4 eBook Output

The production eBook measures 51.8 MB with 6,620 pages and 483 table-of-contents entries. The 181 SOP records included represent unique documents with available PDF renditions (excluding duplicates and documents without renderable content).

5.5 Explorer Output

The interactive HTML explorer weighs 559 KB as a single self-contained file. It displays 185 unique documents (duplicates filtered), 169 graph nodes, 124 graph edges, and 165 PDF mappings across 10 workflows. The difference between 253 relationship nodes and 169 explorer nodes reflects the duplicate filtering and the removal of nodes without document metadata.

5.6 Success Criteria

All pre-defined success criteria were met: document extraction exceeded the >95% target at 100% (253/253), workflow mapping exceeded the >80% coverage target with 470 assignments and 0 unmatched documents, all four knowledge graph formats were generated, the eBook achieved full content coverage (51.8 MB, 6,620 pages), all five agent skill tools passed testing, and all format conversions completed without errors (16/16 .doc files, 165/165 PDF renditions).

6 Discussion

6.1 Keyword vs. Semantic Classification

The keyword-based workflow classification is a deliberate trade-off between sophistication and auditability. Pharmaceutical organizations operate under regulatory scrutiny that values transparency and reproducibility; a classification system where the mapping logic is fully visible in a YAML configuration file (keyword lists plus manual overrides) may be preferable to a black-box embedding model, even if the latter achieves higher automated accuracy.

The 83 manual overrides (approximately 33% of unique documents) indicate that keyword matching alone is insufficient for complete automation. However, the override mechanism provides a structured path for domain expert correction that preserves an audit trail. In practice, the initial keyword-based pass correctly classified the majority of documents, with manual overrides addressing edge cases such as documents with ambiguous titles or atypical content structure.

6.2 Duplicate Handling

The vault directory structure contained 84 subdirectory copies of documents, yielding 269 UDM files from 185 unique sources. The pipeline distinguishes these by appending subdirectory suffixes to document IDs; downstream stages then filter to unique documents only. Content hashing could improve deduplication in future versions.

6.3 Word COM Dependency

The .doc conversion and .docx-to-PDF rendition stages depend on Microsoft Word COM automation via pywin32. This introduces a platform dependency (Windows only) and a software dependency (Microsoft Word v16.0+) that limits the system's portability. Alternative approaches such as LibreOffice headless mode or cloud-based conversion services could relax this constraint at the potential cost of formatting fidelity. For the target use case—a pharmaceutical organization with standardized Windows workstations and Microsoft Office licenses—this dependency is acceptable.

6.4 Scalability Considerations

The current system processes 253 documents in a single sequential pipeline run. The extraction and mapping stages are embarrassingly parallel and could be distributed across multiple workers for larger document libraries. The knowledge graph generation stage loads all UDM files into memory; for very large libraries (>10,000 documents), a streaming approach would be necessary.

The self-contained HTML explorer embeds all data as inline JSON, which scales linearly with document count. For libraries exceeding approximately 1,000 documents, a client-server architecture with API-based data loading would likely be necessary to maintain acceptable load times and file sizes.

6.5 Comparison with Manual Approaches

Prior to the automated pipeline, SOP navigation in the target organization relied on keyword searches within the enterprise document management system, supplemented by team-maintained reference documents (spreadsheets, wikis) mapping SOPs to functional areas. These manual approaches suffer from three recurring problems: incomplete coverage (newly added SOPs may not be indexed), stale classifications (as document content evolves, manual categorizations drift), and invisible cross-references (procedural dependencies between documents are only captured when someone manually traces them).

The automated system addresses each of these:

- **Completeness:** Every document in the vault is classified and cross-referenced, eliminating gaps in manually maintained inventories. The pipeline’s 100% extraction rate ensures no SOP is overlooked.
- **Consistency:** Classification criteria are defined in version-controlled YAML configuration files rather than individual memory. Re-running the pipeline after SOP library updates produces a fresh, consistent classification.
- **Cross-reference visibility:** The knowledge graph surfaces procedural dependencies that are difficult to maintain manually. The 439 relationship edges discovered by automated cross-reference extraction far exceed what manual inventories typically capture.
- **Multi-format access:** The same underlying knowledge serves PDF readers, web browsers, AI agents, and data pipelines, reducing the need for format-specific documentation efforts.

The system also accelerates onboarding. New analysts can browse the explorer to find which SOPs govern their workflow, follow cross-reference links to related procedures, and use the graph visualization to see how documents connect, rather than relying on experienced colleagues for guidance.

6.6 Limitations

1. **No semantic understanding:** The keyword-based classification does not capture document intent or contextual meaning. A document describing “ADaM validation” would match both “Data Transformation” (keyword: ADaM) and “Quality Assurance” (keyword: validation) without distinguishing the primary focus.
2. **Static output:** The pipeline produces a snapshot of the SOP library at a given point in time. It does not monitor the enterprise document management system for updates, additions, or retirements.
3. **Section detection heuristics:** PDF section detection relies on text patterns (numbered headings, uppercase text) rather than semantic style information, producing lower-quality section hierarchies than the DOCX parser.
4. **Template extraction coverage:** Template identification is limited to sections with “template” or “appendix” in their title and placeholder fields marked with curly braces. Custom template formats are not detected.
5. **Single-organization validation:** The system was tested against one organization’s SOP library. The workflow taxonomy and keyword lists reflect the conventions of that specific biostatistics division; other organizations may require taxonomy adjustments and different keyword sets.

6.7 Practical Implications

For organizations considering automated SOP knowledge management, this work offers four practical takeaways. First, keyword-based classification with manual overrides provides a pragmatic starting point that avoids the opacity of machine learning approaches. Second, the multi-format output strategy lets teams adopt whichever format fits their toolchain without requiring the full system. Third, self-contained HTML outputs suit the security-conscious, infrastructure-constrained environments common in regulated pharma. Finally, the 2,500 lines of Python needed for the full pipeline shows that meaningful SOP knowledge automation is within reach for teams with moderate development resources.

7 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presented a six-stage automated pipeline for transforming pharmaceutical SOP libraries into knowledge systems with multiple output formats. Applied to a production corpus of 253 documents, the system demonstrated complete extraction coverage, lifecycle-based classification across 10 operational workflows, and generation of diverse output formats including a 6,620-page PDF eBook, a 559 KB interactive web explorer, and a multi-format knowledge graph.

The architecture prioritizes practical deployment in regulated pharmaceutical environments: keyword-based classification ensures auditability, self-contained outputs eliminate infrastructure dependencies, and manual override mechanisms preserve domain expert authority over automated classifications.

Future Directions

Planned enhancements include:

1. **Semantic search and embeddings:** Augmenting keyword matching with document embeddings (e.g., BioBERT or PubMedBERT) could improve classification accuracy for ambiguous documents while maintaining the override mechanism for expert correction.
2. **LLM-based classification:** Large language models could provide zero-shot or few-shot workflow classification, potentially reducing the number of manual overrides required. Integration would need to address the reproducibility and auditability requirements of regulated environments.
3. **Live document management system integration:** Connecting the pipeline to the enterprise document management system API would enable automatic detection of new, updated, or retired SOPs, producing incremental knowledge graph updates rather than full rebuilds.
4. **Version comparison:** Adding diff-based analysis between SOP versions would surface procedural changes, enabling impact analysis when upstream SOPs are revised.
5. **Natural language querying:** Coupling the knowledge graph with a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) system would allow practitioners to ask natural language questions about SOP content and receive contextually grounded answers with source citations.

Data Availability

The complete pipeline source code, workflow taxonomy, and explorer template are publicly available at <https://github.com/yanmingyu92/sop-knowledge-graph>. The pipeline is implemented in Python 3.11+ (2,500 lines across seven modules). Input SOP documents are excluded from the repository due to proprietary restrictions. The architecture, configuration schemas, and output format specifications described here are sufficient to replicate the system against any pharmaceutical SOP collection in .docx, .pdf, or .doc format.

AI Disclosure

Portions of the pipeline code and this manuscript were developed with assistance from Claude (Anthropic). All technical content, metrics, and architectural decisions were verified by the author against production outputs. The author takes full responsibility for accuracy of all reported results.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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Contributorship Statement

Jaime Yan: study design, system development, data analysis, and manuscript preparation.

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